

INVESTIGATION OF THE CAUSES OF LIMB AMPUTATION. IS IT POSSIBLE TO PREVENT? A SINGLE CENTER STUDY

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Keywords

Amputation

Extremities

Limb salvage

Peripheral arterial disease

Diabetes mellitus

ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to identify the causes of limb amputation and to assess the preventability of amputations. This cross-sectional study was conducted at the Sivas Cumhuriyet University Application and Research Hospital, covering individuals who underwent limb amputation between 01.01.2012 and 30.08.2022. The dependent variable in our study is the occurrence of amputations. The independent variables include the time period, the demographic characteristics of the patients (age, gender), the organ amputated, and the cause of amputation. A total of 746 amputation procedures were performed on 425 patients. Of the patients, 72.5% were male. The average age was 65.5±22.2 years, with a median age of 69.0 years. When the distribution of patients by age groups was examined, individuals aged 80 and above accounted for 31.5% of all patients. Of the amputations performed, 38.4% were due to vascular diseases, 26.8% were caused by trauma, and 25.9% were related to diabetes. The most common sites of amputation were the right foot toes (16.0%) and the left foot toes (13.6%). Re-amputation was performed in 113 patients (26.5%). Of the male patients who underwent amputation, 55.5% were aged 65 and above. The leading causes of amputation in men were vascular diseases, trauma, and diabetes. Among female patients, 70.1% were aged 65 and above. In women, the most frequent causes of amputation were vascular diseases, diabetes, and trauma. When the diagnosis was compared with gender, vascular diseases were found to be the most common cause of amputation in both genders. Analysis of the relationship between age groups and diagnoses revealed that as age increased, the rate of amputations related to vascular diseases and diabetes also increased. Limb amputations are largely associated with preventable health issues, and their rates can be reduced through early diagnosis, regular follow-up, and appropriate treatment strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Limb amputation is one of the oldest surgical procedures, with a history spanning over 2500 years, dating back to the time of Hippocrates¹⁻². The loss of any limb often leads to significant economic, social, and psychological distress, frequently resulting in individuals continuing their lives with a disability. There are many causes of limb loss, with the most common being congenital anomalies, trauma, infections, vascular diseases, and tumors³. Among these causes, amputations due to congenital defects are less common compared to other causes⁴. In bacterial infections, amputations are almost always associated with gangrenous or ulcerated limbs, though severe limb infections such as gas gangrene or necrotizing fasciitis are rare causes of limb loss. The two most important causes of extremity amputation are typically trauma and non-traumatic vascular insufficiency⁵. Aging, diabetes mellitus, chronic kidney disease, hyperlipidemia, hypertension, and congestive heart failure are chronic conditions that trigger vascular occlusion both hemodynamically and structurally, leading to amputation⁶. A study conducted in the United States found that amputations due to vascular diseases account for 82% of all amputations, and this study also highlighted a significant increase in amputations caused by vascular diseases (27%), which was associated with increased life expectancy. Recent studies have indicated a decrease in amputations due to tumors or malignancy and trauma, while the number of amputations caused by congenital deformities has neither increased nor decreased⁵. To date, the causes and characteristics of extremity amputation in Sivas province have not been comprehensively investigated. Understanding the distribution of these causes will aid in the planning of future public health policies, including those for the Sivas region.

This study aims to determine the primary causes and characteristics of extremity amputations in a university hospital setting, examine the temporal trends of amputation causes over the past decade,

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and explore the preventability of limb loss.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This cross-sectional study included individuals who underwent extremity amputation at Sivas Cumhuriyet University Application and Research Hospital between 01.01.2012 and 30.08.2022. No sampling was performed, and all patients who underwent extremity amputation during the specified period were included in the study. The dependent variable in the study is the occurrence of amputation. Independent variables include the time period (01.01.2012-30.08.2022), patients' demographic characteristics (age, gender), and clinical features (cause of amputation and the organ amputated). The age variable was categorized into four groups: 0-44, 45-64, 65-79, and 80 and above. The causes of amputation were classified as congenital anomalies, vascular diseases, diabetes, infections, trauma, and tumors. Data were analyzed using the SPSS-22 statistical software (SPSS INC., Chicago, IL, USA). Descriptive data regarding the patients were prepared; continuous data were presented as mean and standard deviation (minimum-maximum values), while categorical data were presented as counts and percentage distributions. The distribution over the years was shown in a line graph, excluding 2022 as it was not fully included in the study period. Permission numbered 2022-09/31 was obtained for this study from the Sivas Cumhuriyet University Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee.

RESULTS

Between 01.01.2012 and 30.08.2022, a total of 746 amputation procedures were performed on 425 patients. Of these patients, 72.5% (n=308) were male. The average age was 65.5 ± 22.2 (min 7, max 104), with a median age of 69.0 years. When examining the distribution of patients by age group, those aged 80 and above accounted for 31.5% (n=134) of all patients (Table 1). The youngest patient (7 years old) underwent amputation due to trauma, while the oldest patient (104 years old) underwent amputation due to vascular reasons. Of the amputation procedures performed, 38.4% (n=163) were due to vascular diseases, 26.8% (n=114) were caused by trauma, and 25.9% (n=110) were due to diabetes. The most frequently amputated organs were the right foot toes (16.0%, n=68) and the left foot toes (13.6%) (Table 1). The highest number of amputations occurred in 2014 (16.0%, n=68) and 2016 (12.5%, n=53) (Figure 1). Re-amputation was performed in 113 patients (26.5%).

Among male patients who underwent amputation, 55.5% (n=171) were aged 65 and above. The most frequent causes of amputation in men were vascular diseases (35.4%, n=109), trauma (29.9%, n=92), and diabetes (24.4%, n=75). In men, the most commonly amputated organs were the right foot toes (17.9%, n=55) and the left foot toes (13.0%, n=40) (Table 1). The average age of male patients was 63.1 ± 21.9 (min 7, max 104) (Table 1). The highest number of amputations in male patients occurred in 2016 (n=51) (Figure 1).

Among female patients, 70.1% (n=82) were aged 65 and above. The most frequent causes of amputation in women were vascular diseases (46.2%, n=54), diabetes (29.9%, n=35), and trauma (18.8%, n=22). The most frequently amputated organs in women were the left below-knee (18.8%, n=22) and the left foot toes (15.4%, n=18) (Table 1). The mean age of female patients was 71.8 ± 21.7 (min 9, max 102) (Table 1). The highest number of amputations in female patients occurred in 2015 (n=18) (Figure 1).

The mean ages for amputations due to congenital anomalies, tumors, trauma, infections, vascular diseases, and diabetes were 9.0, 45.5, 49.2, 67.3, 70.9, and 75.7 years, respectively (Table 1).

When comparing age groups with gender in the study group, nearly half of the amputation cases in women (44.4%) were observed in those aged 80 and above. In men, however, the amputation rate in the 0-44 age group is significantly higher compared to women. A statistically significant relationship was found between age groups and gender ($p=0.004$) (Table 3).

When comparing diagnoses with gender, vascular diseases were the most common cause of amputation in both genders. Trauma was more prevalent in men, while diabetes was the second leading cause of amputation in women. However, the relationship between gender and diagnosis was not statistically significant ($p=0.054$) (Table 3).

In men, the amputation rate of the right foot toes (17.9%) was higher than that in women (11.1%). Similarly, the amputation rate of the left foot toes was lower in men (13.0%) compared to women (15.4%). The rate of below-knee amputations on the left leg was higher in women (18.8%) than in men (9.1%). Hand and leg amputations were more common in men compared to women. No statistically significant difference was found between the type of amputated organ and gender

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of the patients in the study group

Variables (n=425)	n	%	Mean age ±	Min - Max
Gender				
Female	117	27.5	71.8 ± 21.7	9-102
Male	308	72.5	63.1 ± 21.9	7-104
Age				
Mean age			65.5 ± 22.2	7- 104
Reason of amputation				
Vascular	163	38.4	70.9 ± 21.7	7- 104
Trauma	114	26.8	49.2 ± 22.2	8- 96
Diabetes	110	25.9	75.7 ± 11.2	51-98
Infection	30	7.1	67.3 ± 17.4	36-93
Tumors	7	1.6	45.5 ± 16.0	23-69
Congenital	1	0.2	9.0 ± 0.0	9- 9
Age distribution				
0-44	80	18.8		
45-64	92	21.6		
65-79	119	28.0		
80 and above	134	31.5		
Amputated organ				
Right toes	68	16.0		
Left toes	58	13.6		
Below the left knee	50	11.8		
Left leg	44	10.4		
Right fingers	42	9.9		
Right leg	40	9.4		
Left hand fingers	38	8.9		
Below the right knee	35	8.2		
Right foot	17	4.0		
Left foot	9	2.1		
Right hand	7	1.6		
Left hand	6	1.4		
Right arm	6	1.4		
Left arm	5	1.2		

Table 2. Analysis of gender and other variables in the research group

Variable (n=425)	Total Number %	Female (n= 117) n %	Male (n= 308) n %	p
Age Gro-ups				
0-44	80 18.8	15 12.8	65 21.1	0.004
45-64	92 21.6	20 17.1	72 23.4	
65-79	119 18.0	30 25.6	89 28.9	
80 and above	134 31.5	52 44.4	82 26.6	
Amputation diagnosis				
Vascular	163 38.4	54 46.2	109 35.4	0.054
Trauma	114 26.8	22 18.8	92 29.9	
Diabetes	110 25.9	35 29.9	75 24.4	
Infection	30 7.1	4 3.4	26 8.4	
Tumors	7 1.6	2 1.7	5 1.6	0.121
Congenital	1 0.2	-	1 0.3	
Amputated organ				
Right toes	68 16.0	13 11.1	55 17.9	
Left toes	58 13.6	18 15.4	40 13.0	
Below the left knee	50 11.8	22 18.8	28 9.1	
Left leg	44 10.4	12 10.3	32 10.4	
Right fingers	42 9.9	10 8.5	32 10.4	
Right leg	40 9.4	12 10.3	28 9.1	
Left hand fingers	38 8.9	10 8.5	28 9.1	
Below the right knee	35 8.2	10 8.5	25 8.1	
Right foot	17 4.0	2 1.7	15 4.9	
Left foot	9 2.1	5 4.3	4 1.3	
Right hand	7 1.6	1 0.9	6 1.9	
Left hand	6 1.4	-	6 1.9	
Right arm	6 1.4	1 0.9	5 1.6	
Left arm	5 1.2	1 0.9	4 1.3	

Figure 1. Gender distribution of patients in the study group by year.

($p=0.121$) (Table 3).

In many studies, it has been observed that amputation rates increase in elderly individuals⁸. Authors have stated that

Table 3. Relationship between age groups and diagnoses

Age Group	Vascular		Diabetes		Trauma		Tumor		Infection		Conjenital		P
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
0-44	18	22.5	0	0.0	52	65.0	4	5.0	5	6.3	1	1.3	<0.001
45-64	36	39.1	22	23.9	28	30.4	2	2.2	4	4.3	0	0.0	
65-79	38	31.9	47	39.5	21	17.6	1	0.8	12	10.1	0	0.0	
80 and above	71	53.0	41	30.6	13	9.7	0	0.0	9	6.7	0	0.0	

According to Table 3, which analyzes the relationship between age groups and diagnoses, the majority of amputations due to tumors occurred in the 0-44 age group. No amputations due to tumors were observed in patients aged 80 and above. More than half of the patients who underwent amputation due to vascular diseases were aged 80 and over (53.0%). As age increases, the rate of amputations related to vascular diseases and diabetes also increases. Trauma-related amputations were most prevalent in the 0-44 age group. The relationship between age groups and diagnoses was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

In this study, the frequency and causes of extremity amputations between 2012 and 2022 were examined, and their relationships with age, gender, and other demographic factors were analyzed. According to the study findings, the most common causes of amputations were vascular diseases, trauma, and diabetes. These findings are largely consistent with the existing literature, although some differences were observed in certain aspects. Our study revealed higher amputation rates in male patients and an increased need for amputation in elderly individuals. This supports the role of age and gender in amputation outcomes, which has been emphasized in the literature previously⁷⁻⁹. The strong relationship between age and the risk of amputation is frequently highlighted in the literature. The higher amputation rates in elderly individuals can be attributed to the increased prevalence of arterial diseases, diabetes, and cardiovascular conditions in this population. As individuals age, the treatment of these conditions becomes more challenging, and recovery processes are prolonged, which can increase the need for amputations¹⁰.

vascular diseases and diabetes are significant factors that increase the risk of amputation in older adults¹¹⁻¹². In studies, it has been found that with increasing age, the risk of postoperative complications rises, and survival times tend to be shorter¹³. In our study, similar to the literature, an increase in amputation rates was observed as the mean age rose, and this increase is also reflected in the group distribution where individuals aged 80 and older constitute 31.5% of the total patients. These findings highlight the growing need for amputations with age and the challenges in the recovery process.

The effect of gender on extremity amputations is another frequently discussed topic in the literature. It has been reported that men, especially those with vascular diseases and trauma, have higher amputation rates⁷.

Specifically, it has been reported that limb loss in young men is significantly higher compared to women. This trend shows an increase in men over the years, while women continue to experience a steady increase in amputation rates without significant changes¹⁴. In our study, it was also observed that men experience amputation due to diabetes at a younger age, a finding supported by other studies, which suggest that this could be due to various factors. In women, diabetes, particularly in elderly individuals, is a significant risk factor for increased amputation rates, and the post-amputation mortality rate is higher in women compared to men¹⁵.

The study data show results similar to the literature, but the different effects of gender stem from men having higher amputation rates due to acute events like trauma, while women are more affected by the pronounced effects of diabetes and vascular diseases. Moreover, the fact that the women in the study group were generally older, with vascular diseases being more prevalent in this age group, is likely to have contributed

to the higher amputation rates.

Extremity amputations are generally the result of chronic diseases such as vascular diseases, trauma, and diabetes. The literature emphasizes that peripheral artery disease (PAD) and diabetes are among the most common causes of limb loss¹⁶.

Vascular diseases, especially peripheral artery disease and arterial diseases, can reduce blood flow and lead to gangrene in tissues, resulting in amputations. Additionally, diabetes, combined with peripheral neuropathy and microvascular complications, impedes the healing of foot wounds, further increasing the risk of amputation¹⁷. Trauma, particularly in developing countries, is another significant factor leading to extremity loss in younger age groups¹⁸.

However, in elderly individuals, trauma generally leads to a lower rate of amputation, while chronic diseases such as vascular diseases and diabetes are more likely to cause the need for amputation¹⁹. Studies indicate that the risk of amputation increases in older patients, and these individuals tend to have poorer responses to treatment²⁰. In our study, 38.4% of amputations were due to vascular diseases, 26.8% were caused by trauma, and 25.9% were related to diabetes. These findings are consistent with the existing literature.

Furthermore, considering the cause-effect relationship, it can be observed that approximately 65-70% of amputations could be reduced with appropriate preventive measures. Peripheral artery disease (PAD), particularly in relation to metabolic diseases such as diabetes, is a significant complication that can lead to extremity amputations. Early diagnosis, management of risk factors, and a multidisciplinary approach are crucial. Lifestyle changes such as controlling blood sugar levels, quitting smoking, antihypertensive treatment, and lipid management can slow the progression of PAD²¹.

For diabetic patients, early diagnosis, regular foot care, blood sugar control, and lifestyle changes play a significant role in preventing amputations. Numerous studies have shown that early detection of diabetic foot complications and appropriate treatment can significantly reduce amputation rates. Moreover, managing diabetes by keeping blood sugar levels under control, quitting smoking, and adopting regular physical activity can help prevent amputations by reducing the risk of complications²².

For the sustainability of this process, it is important to educate both patients and healthcare professionals about early

diagnosis and intervention. Studies have shown that educating diabetic individuals about foot care and regular screening by healthcare professionals reduce amputation rates²³.

With early diagnosis, proper wound management, and appropriate treatment approaches, diabetic amputations can be significantly prevented²⁴.

In conclusion, limb loss usually results from a combination of multiple factors, and managing these factors is crucial for reducing the risk of amputation. The fluctuations in amputation rates over the years are associated with the accessibility of healthcare services, advancements in surgical techniques, and changes in disease burden. In our study, it was observed that the highest number of amputations occurred in 2014 and 2016. The increase in the number of amputations in these years can be attributed to better access to healthcare services, advancements in surgical methods, and changes in patients' clinical conditions. Recent research also emphasizes that annual fluctuations in amputation rates are typically related to changes in patients' health conditions and the development of healthcare systems. Changes in annual amputation rates are linked to improvements in healthcare policies and clinical practices²⁵.

In this study, 26.5% of the 113 patients who underwent amputation required reoperation. The literature indicates that postoperative complications, particularly vascular issues, can increase the need for re-amputation. It has been reported that re-amputation generally occurs due to infections in the healing process or the progression of vascular diseases²⁶. Re-amputations are often caused by postoperative complications, and early interventions are necessary to prevent this²⁷. Factors such as diabetes, hyperlipidemia, smoking, and stump trauma have been identified as determinants for the need for reoperation²⁸.

Advanced age, American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) class 4 patients, concomitant neurological diseases, low albumin levels, low lymphocyte count, and the need for postoperative intensive care unit (ICU) admission are poor prognostic factors for survival²⁹. These factors can significantly increase the risk of mortality and morbidity in patients, representing a serious issue that needs to be carefully considered¹¹.

Prevention of extremity amputations may be achievable through the development of early diagnosis and treatment methods. By controlling diabetes and vascular diseases, as

well as implementing foot care and regular screening programs, amputation rates can be reduced²⁹. Additionally, increasing safety measures to prevent trauma and reducing traffic accidents are crucial. Early treatment and preventive measures can substantially lower amputation rates.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the causes of extremity amputations and their relationship with age, gender, and other demographic factors, comparing the results with existing literature. Vascular diseases, trauma, and diabetes are the most common causes of amputations. It is also evident that with increasing age, both amputation rates and the need for subsequent surgeries can rise.

When considering the diseases leading to amputation, early intervention, treatment, and lifestyle changes can help prevent amputations. Health policies that prioritize early diagnosis and treatment processes and develop strategies to reduce amputation rates will be of critical importance in the future, especially considering the aging global population.

This study has some limitations, including its cross-sectional and retrospective design, which prevents establishing cause-and-effect relationships. The research was conducted in a single university hospital, which may limit the generalizability of the results. Additionally, the study did not explore long-term post-amputation outcomes or consider socioeconomic factors like income and education, which can affect amputation rates and access to healthcare.

However, the study has notable strengths. It uses a large sample of 425 patients, providing valuable insights into the causes and trends of amputations over a 10-year period. The inclusion of demographic factors like age and gender enhances the depth of the analysis. Ethical approval was obtained, ensuring adherence to ethical standards, and the use of robust statistical methods strengthens the validity of the findings. This study provides practical insights for healthcare providers and policymakers, particularly in the Sivas region.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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No

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